

ASPERGER SYNDROME: SHORT STORY OF A DIAGNOSIS. AN OPINION

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Asperger Syndrome (AS) is a form of autism, considered once a different diagnostic, assimilated sometimes with high functioning autism but subsumed now under the larger spectrum of autism disorder. Several studies show the association between Asperger disorder and the sense of personal self, social identity, and community membership, and that the change in diagnosis could affect the mental health and psychological wellbeing of Asperger people. Our goals in writing this article are to raise awareness about the changes in the diagnosis and to point out how people living with Asperger syndrome are affected.

Keywords: Asperger, diagnostic, DSM

INTRODUCTION

Asperger Syndrome (AS) is a form of autism, considered once a different diagnostic, assimilated sometimes with high functioning autism but subsumed now under the larger spectrum of autism disorder.

In this paper, we use the terms “Asperger syndrome”/“Asperger disorder” and “autism spectrum condition” (ASC) /”autism spectrum disorder” (ASD) as similar, due to the official terminology in DSM (disorder) and the less stigmatizing term used in communities (condition).

In DSM V, there is no more Asperger Syndrome or Disorder. In the medical view, Asperger people are autistic individuals with high abilities to use language and communication, with an I. Q. in the normal range, sometimes even higher, and with some difficulties in social behavior and relationships.

But for Asperger people, this was not just a diagnosis. It was a group of similar people, a sense of identity, a way out of isolation. For them, losing the diagnostic seems like losing their own identity or self.

Our goals in writing this article are to raise awareness about the changes in the diagnostic and to point out how the people living with Asperger syndrome are affected.

THE HISTORY OF TERMS

The term “autist” was first used by Eugen Bleuler, in 1911, to describe schizophrenic patients who appeared disconnected from the outside world. Later, in 1943 and, respectively, 1944, Leo Kanner and Hans Asperger used the term “autism” as a standalone diagnosis to describe certain characteristics of social withdrawal (Kanner, 1943; Asperger, 1944).

The term ‘autism’, which comes from the Greek word *autós*, meaning self, suggests that there is a lack of self-awareness as a central element of autism spectrum condition (ASC) (Lombardo *et al.*, 2010).

Kanner, seen as the “father” of American child psychiatry, published his work on autism, “Autistic Disturbances of Affective Contact,” in 1943. He described children as socially and emotionally withdrawn, and preoccupied with objects and rituals – with repetitive behavior, little to no speech, and severe cognitive impairments. For many years, this description was the standard for what was called “classic,” or Kanner-type autism, for all the practitioners in the United States and many other countries. The children were described as having difficulties in social interactions, difficulties in adapting to changes in routines, good memory, sensitivity to stimuli (especially auditive), resistance and allergies to food, good intellectual potential, echolalia, or propensity to repeat words of the speaker and difficulties in spontaneous activity.

The same year, in Vienna, Asperger presented his postdoctoral thesis, “The ‘Autistic Psychopaths’ in Childhood,” which he published in 1944 (Asperger, 1944).

Asperger’s definition of autistic psychopathy was much broader, and included those he saw with far milder challenges: fluent speech, medium intelligence level, social abilities that give them sometimes the possibility to attend standard school but not enough for social integration, but compensating sometimes by “a high level of original thought and experience”. Asperger’s diagnosis remained little known for decades until the psychiatrist Lorna Wing discovered Asperger’s 1944 thesis and publicized the diagnosis in 1981 as “Asperger’s syndrome” (Wing, 1981).

Later, Uta Frith translated and publicized Asperger’s original thesis in *Autism and Asperger Syndrome*, in 1991. (Asperger, 1991). The diagnosis was recognized and the idea took off in psychiatric circles, and in 1994 Asperger Syndrome became an official psychiatric diagnosis in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders IVth edition (DSM IV).

ASPERGER DISORDER. DIAGNOSTIC AND DEFINITION

The American Psychiatric Association recognized the diagnosis of autism in 1980 when the 3rd edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders was published. In the section Schizophrenic Disorders, Infantile

autism/Kanner's syndrome was described by these symptoms: stereotyped repetitive movements, hyperkinesis, self-injury, retarded speech development, echolalia, and impaired social relationships, and, often, mental retardation (APA, 1980).

After Asperger syndrome was described by Lorna Wing in 1981 and his thesis published by Uta Frith in 1991, The American Psychiatric Association introduced the "Asperger disorder" as a diagnostic category in the DSM IV in 1994 (APA, 1994). The essential features of Asperger disorder were the presence of markedly abnormal or impaired development in social interaction and communication and a markedly restricted repertoire of activity and interests, and it was distinguished from 'autistic disorder' by a lack of significant delay in language and general cognition. The term Asperger syndrome has become popular, and there has been a great deal of research comparing those with this diagnosis to those with autism. A lot of children and adults were diagnosed with Asperger Disorder and they established communities, and social groups, and helped each other with social integration. Also, due to their communication skills and level of intelligence, thousands of studies and scientific experiments were conducted on Asperger subjects and the data from literature are rich in information about emotions, social impairments, way of thinking, and their different life perspectives.

Compared with Asperger syndrome, Infantile autism is a syndrome described by abnormal responses to auditory and sometimes visual stimuli and severe problems in the understanding of spoken language. Speech is delayed and or characterized by echolalia, the reversal of pronouns, immature grammatical structure, and inability to use abstract terms or concepts. Difficulties in social relationships appear before the age of four-five years and include impairments in the development of eye-to-eye contact, social attachments, and cooperative play. Ritualistic behavior is usual and may include stereotyped patterns of play. The ability to use abstract or symbolic concepts and for imaginative play is diminished (APA, DSM 4).

In the DSM V (APA, 2013) and ICD 11 (WHO, 2019) the Asperger disorder, often understood as "high-functioning" autism, was removed as a diagnostic and merged with Autistic Disorder, Rett's Disorder, Childhood Disintegrative Disorder, and Pervasive Developmental Disorder Not Otherwise Specified in a generic category of Autism Spectrum Disorder, under the Neurodevelopmental Disorders category. Autism spectrum disorder is characterized by deficits in social communication and social interaction, and by restricted, repetitive patterns of behavior, interests, or activities. The new categories of autism are delimited by the level of needed support ("support", "substantial support", "very substantial support").

INCIDENCE

According to the United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the number of children classified with autism spectrum disorders rose from 1 in 2,500 in 1985 to 1 in 500 in 1995. As Asperger's work became mainstream,

rates of diagnoses continued to rise from 1 in 150 children in 2002 to 1 in 68 children by 2016 (Baoi J., 2010)

Using DSM V criteria, about 1 in 54 children has been identified with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) according to estimates from CDC's Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring (ADDM) Network in the USA. (Maenner M. J., 2020) Several studies show that for every three cases of ASD that are diagnosed in children of primary school age, two more cases remain unrecognized (Baron-Cohen *et al.*, 2009).

No available data on Asperger disorder incidence in the world were found. Many affected persons probably have reached adulthood and never have been diagnosed or receive age-specific support in childhood or adolescence (Pilling *et al.*, 2012; Lenhardt *et al.*, 2013). The moment they ask for medical or psychiatric help, they often suffer from anxiety, depression, severe communication impairments, and social life difficulties. Despite their high level of education, often these people have low socio-economical status, low self-esteem, and impairments in keeping long-term relationships or families (Lugnegård *et al.*, 2011).

The changes in diagnostic criteria in the DSM V and ICD 11 will affect even more Asperger people. The number of undiagnosed individuals will grow or they will receive a different diagnosis, like social communication disorder (SCD). In a recent study from South Korea, the estimated prevalence of DSM-V criteria ASD is 2.20%. Most children with Autistic Disorder (99%), Asperger Disorder (92%), and PDD NOS (63%) met DSM-V ASD criteria, whereas 1%, 8%, and 32%, respectively, met SCD criteria (Kim *et al.*, 2014).

Due to their average or high IQ and the camouflage effect (Rinkiewicz *et al.*, 2016] Asperger people have a higher risk of underdiagnosis or not receiving the appropriate diagnosis. Several studies have shown that many affected persons probably reach adulthood without receiving a proper diagnosis and, consequently, proper support for their condition. Furthermore, 70% of the affected persons develop comorbid disturbances, anxiety, and depression in adulthood and if they seek medical help, the manifestations of these secondary disturbances may lead to difficulties in both differential diagnosis and treatment, because they could never receive the autistic diagnosis and could be treated only for comorbidities (Cath *et al.*, 2008).

EFFECTS ON ASPERGER PEOPLE

People with Asperger Syndrome are very sensitive people, with complex perspectives concerning the self and identity concepts, sometimes affected by anxiety, depression, and other comorbidities. Stigma about the autistic traits or Asperger Syndrome traits affects the way an individual constructs his sense of self, his relations with others, with neurotypical people, or with neurodivergent people.

They can accept the diagnosis, the condition as a gift, gives them a sense of self (personal identity) or membership in a group of similar people (social identity),

or they can reject the diagnosis, and put it outside of their true self (Hickey *et al.*, 2018). Qualitative research on autistic adults indicates that identity construction may be challenging for those diagnosed later in life. In a study of autistic individuals who received their diagnosis earlier in life, they expressed more acceptance of being autistic and a more positive sense of self (Cox *et al.*, 2017). Social identities relate to psychological perceptions of group memberships and form part of the self-concept. Socially identifying with groups has previously been found to associate with better mental well-being outcomes (Maitland *et al.*, 2021).

For Asperger people, Asperger diagnosis was more than a diagnosis and an explanation for their condition and struggles, it was an opportunity to build a sense of self, a personal and social identity. Taking away the group, the name, and the community is like taking away their self and their support. Some of them don't see the diagnosis as a disorder, but as a gift: "In order to determine whether AS is a disability or a gift, I have to ask myself if I am truly disabled. Of course I prefer differently-abled. We are overly-abled in some areas, super-enabled even. We can read books and understand anything written better than most, but can't follow social conversation. We can dismantle computers and install hardware, but we can't find our way around a supermarket" (Simone R., 2010).

"DSM-V is taking away our identity" is the reaction of the online community to the removal of Asperger diagnostic from DSM (Giles D, 2014). Gamlin's research demonstrates how the DSM-5 reclassification has the potential to threaten the identity of those affected, discusses the problem of autism as a stigmatizing diagnostic label, and points out that Asperger diagnosis was valued by patients for its distinctiveness from autism. Also, the study concludes that the new situation brings with it the potential to inflict iatrogenic harm (Gamlin C., 2017).

The stigma associated with the autism condition is an important reason for concern for Asperger people. Stigma can be defined as the social discrediting of attributes that causes individuals to feel unacceptable or 'othered' (Goffman, 1990). Several studies show that there is a direct relationship between camouflaging and experiences of stigma, both qualitative and quantitative. Camouflaging refers to strategies used by autistic people to mask or hide social difficulties. The more bullying and harassment they get, the more they hide their difficulties and they make huge efforts to look "normal". That effort to continuously camouflage is not healthy. Recent studies show an association between social camouflage and depression, anxiety, stress, social anxiety, suicidality, poor well-being, and burnout in autistic people (Beck *et al.*, 2020; Cage E., Troxell-Whitman Z., 2019).

DISCUSSION

The Asperger diagnostic story is simple: in 1994 APA introduced the diagnostic in the DSM IV, as a different diagnostic than autism/Kanner autism and after 19 years, it was removed or submerged under the autism umbrella. The

reasons for that were purely methodological, considering the similarities between high functioning autism and Asperger Syndrome in the after-therapy life. But the level of support is different in childhood and is different in adult life, too. And, in the medical world, the two diagnostics were not similar and could not be interchangeable, due to the different language and communication abilities, which is the main core of the autism problem.

Scientific literature is abundant in studies that show the concern about the Asperger people's identity, the stigma associated with autism, and the communities that offer psychological and social support to Asperger people.

The story of the Asperger diagnosis ends in 2013. But the story of Asperger people will continue for a while, despite the medical methodological reasons.

There are Aspie communities that stand up and fight for their right to be different in a specific way.

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